

Estimating Madagascar economic growth using the Mixed Data Sampling (MIDAS) approach

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Abstract

In this document, we introduce a forecasting model for the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to estimate the economic growth of Madagascar in 2022. Normally, important macroeconomic variables are reported at different frequencies. For instance, GDP and foreign trade figures are typically provided on a quarterly and monthly basis respectively. However, traditional econometric models necessitate data to be harmonized to a common frequency by aggregating at the highest available frequency, which is known as temporal aggregation. Nonetheless, this approach has a disadvantage of losing information. Consequently, we propose the Mixed Data Sampling (MIDAS) method as an alternative.

Keywords: MIDAS, economic growth, Madagascar.

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1 Introduction

The forecast of Madagascar's economic growth is primarily based on an accounting approach using leading indicators. This method allows us to examine the evolution of the economy's sectors based on the branches that make up the national accounting on the supply side, thus capturing the potential trend of the real economy. This approach generates an annual forecast using annual frequency data as well. In this document, we will adopt the demand-side approach to estimate the level of GDP and forecast the economic growth of Madagascar in 2022 using the Mixed Data Sampling (MIDAS) approach.

2 Literature review of the model

The Mixed Data Sampling (MIDAS) model, proposed by Ghysels E. and al. (1977), allows for the inclusion of time series with different frequencies in the same regression, overcoming the need for data transformation through aggregation or interpolation. This model can explain the dynamic and structural relationship that is overlooked by temporal data aggregation.

Several authors have used the MIDAS model for macroeconomic forecasting and compared its performance with other models. Michael M. (1911) tested whether a MIDAS approach could improve GDP growth forecasts in the United States. They concluded that using monthly data leads to a significant improvement in current and next-quarter GDP growth forecasts, and that MIDAS outperforms other methods (such as AR and ARDL).

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Kyosuke C. (2021) conducted a GDP forecasting study in Japan based on MIDAS and compared the results with other approaches. Their study showed that MIDAS had better out-of-sample forecast performance. Foroni C. (2012) compared the forecasting performance of MIDAS and U-MIDAS through Monte Carlo simulations. They demonstrated that U-MIDAS outperformed restricted MIDAS when there were small frequency differences among the selected variables in the regression. However, they were comparable for relatively large frequency differences.

The MIDAS model is described by the following equation:

$$PIB_t = \beta_0 + \beta_2 \sum_{k=1}^n b(k; \Theta) L^{\frac{k-1}{m}} X_{t-h}^m + \gamma_1 dm_1 + \gamma_2 dm_2 + \gamma_3 dm_3 + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $b(k; \Theta)$ is an Almon exponential lag;
- t indexes the time unit in quarters;
- m is the highest sampling frequency ;
- $L^{\frac{1}{m}}$ is an operator at the highest frequency ;
- h is the forecast horizon ;
- dm_i represents the dummy variable to capture the seasonal component of the i^{th} trimester;
- X_t represents the vector of explanatory variables.

3 Criteria and Variable Selection

The model used for forecasting/estimation was chosen based on its out-of-sample forecasting performance, measured by the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). RMSE is a measure of the distance between data points and the regression line. Therefore, we select the model with the lowest RMSE, including the following variables: money supply (m3), electricity consumption in the primary sector (elec1), industry (elec2), services (elec3), and fuel consumption Anjum A. and al. (2001).

In the literature, variables such as exports Michael P. (2008), imports Coe D. T. and Helpman E. (1995), money supply Bednarik R. (2010), electricity consumption Nathan R., 1998, and exchange rates (1998) have been used in GDP regression models.

Advocates of export-led growth, such as Michael M. (1911), Bela B. (1978) argues that countries with a significant share of exports tend to grow faster than others. Export growth acts as a stimulus for technology transfer throughout the economy. In Keynesian theory, export growth leads to production expansion Michael M. (1911).

For Keynesians, changes in money supply lead to changes in real production and prices. Konstantins B. (2008) included money supply in their models for forecasting real GDP in Latvia, Romania, and Germany, respectively. In their forecasting models, they used other variables capturing expenditure (exports, imports, and retail trade) and finance (money supply M3).

The use of electricity powers equipment and associated manufacturing facilities. This analysis suggests that the quantity of electricity consumed can capture the trend of GDP. The GDP regression model adopted by Robert Z. and David E. (1999) includes electricity consumption and other associated variables. These studies found a significant relationship between electricity consumption and GDP. Additionally, electricity consumed in the industrial production process is generated by hydroelectric and thermal power plants. Therefore, the energy variable represented by fuel consumption cannot be omitted. Anjum A. and al. (2001) demonstrated that the relationship between economic growth and energy consumption is well-established in the literature, including in developing countries like Pakistan.

Furthermore, variables such as consumption (proxied by the Consumer Price Index, CPI) and investment (public and private) are components of demand, which is another approach to GDP calculation. Moreover, these variables have a major contribution to determining the real evolution of the economy. Regarding economic

openness, exchange rates capture the country’s relationship with the rest of the world [Prudence A. and al. \(1998\)](#). The exchange rates used in this case are the Euro, the Dollar, and the Ariary.

The data in this study have different frequencies. Gross Domestic Product (GDP), the explanatory variable, is expressed on a quarterly basis, while the explanatory variables, including money supply (m3), electricity consumption (elec1, elec2, and elec3), public consumption (cg), public investment (ig), Consumer Price Index (ipc), fuel consumption (carb), and exchange rates (EUR (eur), USD (usd), ARIARY (xg)), are measured on a monthly basis. The variables are transformed using logarithms. The stationarity test at the level has shown that none of these variables is stationary. They all exhibit trend-stationary series. Therefore, a decomposition of these series using the Hodrick-Prescott method is necessary.

4 Estimation and Analysis of Model Performance

The quarterly GDP data covers the period from Q1 2007 to Q2 2022, resulting in 64 observations based on the data provided by INSTAT ¹. On the other hand, the explanatory variables span from January 2007 to December 2022, resulting in 192 observations.

During the estimation process, the model specification used is the PDL-ALMON. This specification allows for the estimation of the MIDAS model and captures the relationship between the quarterly GDP and the explanatory variables.

To analyze the performance of our MIDAS model, we conducted a comparison between the observed GDP data and the estimates generated by the model over the entire period from 2007 to 2022. This comparison enables us to assess the accuracy and reliability of the model’s predictions and evaluate its ability to capture the dynamics of GDP growth.

5 Result

The result of the model provides us with the following figures:

Quarter GDP	2021	2022
Q1	4 665.8	5 213.9
Q2	5 547.1	5 737.1
Q3	5 535.2	5 405.6
Q4	5 737.3	6 133.0
Annual GDP	21 485.4	22 489.7

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)	0.014038
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.011039
Mean Abs. Percent Error (MAPE)	0.130357
R-squared	0.984338

The selected MIDAS model estimated the economic growth rate of Madagascar to be 4.7% for the year 2022.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, the conventional accounting model for Madagascar’s national accounts provides a somewhat realistic forecast at the supply level. The indicators chosen in this approach reflect the actual evolution of the sectors’ branches in the economy. On the other hand, the Mixed Data Sampling Model promotes a demand-oriented approach based on the variables considered potential in the model’s manipulation. This approach offers several advantages in terms of accuracy and comparison with supply-level results. Furthermore, the MIDAS model is among the immediate forecasting models with high-frequency indicators. The model’s result indicates a positive growth trend in 2022, which remains preliminary until the final realization figures are published by the responsible entities.

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